

Lossy compression using square-root coding

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Abstract

The accuracy degradation for a simple square-root coding is estimated analytically. The required number of bits for the AF samples is estimated as function of magnitude. Accepting a 5 per cent degradation of the accuracy, 6 bits per sample are required for the most common stellar magnitudes.

Model of DN

The digital output of a CCD system does not consist of the actual electron counts, but of the "Data Numbers" (DN) obtained after amplification of the analogue signal, application of a suitable offset voltage ("bias") to prevent negative numbers, and quantization (A/D conversion). Apart from the Poisson noise associated with the electron counts, additive noise appears in all stages of the analogue chain. The "readout noise" (RON) consists of all these additive noise sources, plus the quantization noise, expressed as an equivalent rms number of electrons. Neglecting possible non-linearities, a reasonable model for the DN is therefore:

$$n = \text{nint}(N/g + b + w) \quad (1)$$

where:

n = the DN (typically on a 16-bit scale from 0 to 65535)
N = number of electrons (detected photons plus dark counts)
g = "gain" expressed in e/DN
b = "bias" expressed in DN
w = a noise term associated with RON (see below)

In turn, N is modelled as a Poisson process with mean value A (the expected number of counts, or "intensity"), and w is modelled as a gaussian variable with zero mean and variance $(r/g)^2 - 1/12$, where r is the rms RON expressed in e. The variance of the quantization noise is $1/12 \text{ DN}^2$, so the total variance of the RON including quantization noise is r^2 . An alternative way of writing the model is:

$$n = N/g + b + w + q \quad (2)$$

where q is a number between -0.5 and +0.5 required to make n an integer. The variance of (w+q) is $(r/g)^2$.

Typical parameters for AF

The gain g is usually selected to map the full range of N values (from 0 to the maximum charge per sample) onto the 16-bit range

of n ; e.g. for the AF (Table 4.17) $g = 330000/65535 = 5 \text{ e/DN}$. The bias b must be chosen to make n non-negative under all circumstances. The rms value of w is approximately r/g , so an absolute minimum is $b = 3r/g = 3.6$ (for $r = 6$), but often $b = 50-100$ is used to avoid possible problems with drift or variations with temperature. In the following I assume (for AF):

$$\begin{aligned} r &= 6 \\ g &= 5 \\ b &= 20 \end{aligned}$$

Square-root coding

>From (2) the variance of n is found to be:

$$\text{var}(n) = A/g^{**2} + (r/g)^{**2} \quad (3)$$

which depends on the intensity A . The idea of the square-root coding is to apply a non-linear transformation of n which gives approximately constant variance (independent of A) and then round to the nearest integer. The additional variance due to the rounding is then a constant fraction of the variance of the uncoded data (n); i.e., the coding adds a constant percentage to the astrometric and photometric errors. The required transformation is:

$$k = \text{nint}(c*\text{sqrt}(n + d)) \quad (3)$$

where c and d are constants. c determines how much additional variance is added (a large value gives more accurate coding), while d must be chosen as:

$$d = (r^{**2})/g - b \quad (4)$$

to make $\text{var}(k)$ independent of A . With this choice we have:

$$\text{var}(k) = (c^{**2})/(4*g) + 1/12 \quad (5)$$

Note that for systems with very low RON, $r < 3$, it may happen that $(n+d)$ in (3) becomes negative for $N = 0$, if there is an extreme negative fluctuation of w . For such low-noise systems it will be necessary to make d a little larger than in (4).

Decoding error

Given the coded value k , the estimated (decoded) DN is obtained by inverting (3):

$$n_{\text{est}} = (k/c)^{**2} - d \quad (6)$$

>From (1), the estimated electron count is then:

$$N_{\text{est}} = g*(n_{\text{est}} - b) \quad (7)$$

Combining (6) and (7) with (4) gives:

$$N_{\text{est}} = g \cdot (k/c)^2 - r^2 \quad (8)$$

Using (5) and standard error propagation methods gives:

$$\text{var}(N_{\text{est}}) = (A + r^2) \cdot [1 + g/(3c^2)] \quad (9)$$

In the absence of coding the variance would be $A + r^2$. The square-root coding therefore causes a relative increase in the variance by $g/(3c^2)$. The relative increase in the standard error of N_{est} is approximately:

$$\text{relative increase in rms} = g/(6c^2) \quad (10)$$

It is perhaps reasonable to accept a 5 per cent increase in the error budget due to the coding. This requires $c = \sqrt{g/6 \cdot 0.05} = 4$ in our example.

Number of pixels required

For a star of magnitude $G = 20$ the number of detected photons in the PSF of the AF is approximately 350, of which at most about 150 will fall in the central sample (cf. Fig 10.3). The background (dark + sky) is only a few counts. Allowing a $+3\sigma$ fluctuation both in the electron count and in the RON, the maximum N would be 205. With the parameters assumed above ($r = 6$, $g = 5$, $b = 20$, $d = -12.8$, $c = 4$) this gives $n = 45$ and then $k = 23$. The faintest stars can therefore be coded in 5 bits per sample. With 6 bits the maximum is $k = 63$, $n = 260$, $N = 1200$ which is sufficient for $G > 17.9$. See the table below for other values.

bits	k_{max}	n_{max}	N_{max}	G_{min}
5	31	73	265	19.7
6	63	260	1200	17.9
7	127	1020	5000	16.2
8	255	4070	20250	14.7
9	511	16300	81400	13.2
10	1023	65400	327000	11.7

For a complete census to $G = 20$ most stars are fainter than $G = 17.9$, and can thus be coded in 6 bits. The mean number of bits required is only a little more than 6. Note that this is achieved with a 5 per cent increase in the astrometric and photometric errors.

Using a variable number of pixels per sample requires some overhead to specify the number of pixels in each sample. This can be minimized by grouping samples of about the same intensity (requiring the same number of pixels) under the same header. For the AF a natural solution would be to code all the 17×6 samples of a whole transit with the same number of bits (the actually required number can be found out before cutting off the zeroes). The effective compression factor would be approximately 2.5 for the AF samples, compared with the uncoded 16-bit samples. Some additional lossless compression is possible, but probably not by a large factor. To reach a total compression significantly higher than 3 seems

to require a much more sophisticated coding and/or a higher loss of accuracy.

As a general comment, we must avoid transmitting noise that per definition does not contain information, and which cannot be compressed by automatic algorithms (which do not recognize that it is noise). The square-root compression is optimal in this respect since all the known noise (Poisson + RON) is coded into 2-3 bits per sample. (The variance of k is 0.94 in the example above. To code ± 3 sigma noise thus requires 3 bits.) Remaining bits are in a sense "deterministic" and could to a large part be eliminated by a clever algorithm without additional loss of information. Thus there is at least a theoretical possibility to reach a compression of $16/3 = 5$, but this would seem to be about the ultimate limit.
